
Wikidata

**Structured data repository that
anyone can edit**

— Filip Maljković —
PSSOH, October 26, 2019

Two main problems with Wikipedia

1. Outdated data; no triggers for change; boring and repetitive work
 - There's a large number of Wikipedias; some will have updated info, some won't
2. Inflexible ways for fetching specific data
 - Limits of categories
 - Example: all authors whose parents were born in Paris

Two main problems with Wikipedia

One solution for both problems:

Wikidata - central multilingual repository for linked and structured data, on a wiki, that anyone can edit, under a free license

WIKIDATA

Structured data

Statement = Item: property \rightarrow value

- Item (Q) - any topic (person, object, place, concept)
 - Property (P) - specific type of data relevant for an item (e.g. *gender* for people, *capital* for countries, *length* for rivers)
 - Value - either a “literal value” (e.g. length of Danube is 2860 km), or a reference to another item (e.g. capital of Serbia is Belgrade)
-
- Item is described by a set of statements (each statement provides a fact or a data point about an item)

Structured data

- Earth (Q2): highest point (P610) → Mount Everest (Q513)
- Mount Everest (Q513): elevation above sea level (P2044) → 8848 m
- Earth (Q2): lowest point (P1589) → Challenger Deep (Q459173)
- Challenger Deep (Q459173): elevation above sea level (P2044) → -10,994±40 m

Structured data

Or:

- Q2: P610 \rightarrow Q513
- Q513: P2044 \rightarrow 8848 m
- Q2: P1589 \rightarrow Q459173
- Q459173: P2044 \rightarrow -10,994 \pm 1 m

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Item by title
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page

the third planet in the Solar System

Gaia | ⊕ | the world | Blue Planet | Terra Mater | Terra | Planet Earth | Tellus | The Earth | Sol III | Sol 3 | Sol d | ♁

↵ In more languages Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Earth	the third planet in the Solar System	Gaia ⊕ the world Blue Planet Terra Mater Terra Planet Earth Tellus The Earth Sol III Sol 3 Sol d ♁
Croatian	Zemlja	treći unutarnji planet Sunčeva sustava	Svijet Zemlja Majka Zemlja Geja Terra
Serbian	Земља	трећа планета у Сунчевом систему	
српски	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of ⊞ inner planet of the Solar System 0 references

part of ⊞ Solar System 0 references

Wikipedia (238 entries) [Collapse]

- ab Адгъыл
- ace Вумоѳ
- ady Чыгу
- af Aarde 🇺🇸
- als Erde
- am መሬት
- ang Eorðe
- an Tierra
- arc ܐܕܘܪܐ
- ar الأرض 🇺🇸
- arz الارض
- ast Tierra
- as পৃথিৱী
- av Ракъ (планета)
- ay Aka pacha
- azb بئز
- az Yer
- bar Eadn
- bat_smg Žemė
- ba Ер
- bcl Kinaban
- be_x_old Зямля
- be Планета Зямля 🇺🇸
- bg Земя 🇺🇸
- bh धरती
- bjn Bumi
- bn পৃথিবী
- bo ལྗོངས་ལྗོངས་
- br Douar (planedenn)
- bs Zemlja (planeta)
- bxr Дэлхэй
- ca Terra
- cbk_zam Tierra
- cdo Dê-giù

- Localization
- Description
- Aliases
- Interwiki

highest point

Chimborazo	
applies to part	centre
country	Ecuador
1 reference	
reference URL	https://www.theweathernetwork.com/us/news/articles/climate-and-environment/ecuadors-mt-chimborazo-is-officially-highest-spot-on-earth/66219
Mount Everest	
elevation above sea level	8,848±20 metre
applies to part	Earth's surface
country	Nepal
0 references	

deepest point

Challenger Deep	
elevation above sea level	-10,994±40 metre
1 reference	
reference URL	http://abstractsearch.agu.org/meetings/2011/FM/OS13B-1517.html
retrieved	8 January 2017
publication date	2011
Galathea Depth	
end time	1952
elevation above sea level	-10,540±1 metre
1 reference	
imported from	German Wikipedia
Vityas Deep 1	
start time	1957
elevation above sea level	-10,950±50 metre

- hak Thi-khii
- ha Duniya
- haw Honua
- he כדור הארץ
- hif Dunia
- hi पृथ्वी
- hr Zemlja
- hsb Zemja
- ht Latè
- hu Föld
- hy Երկիր
- ia Terra
- id Bumi 🌍
- ie Terra
- ig Àlà
- ilo Daga (planeta)
- io Tero
- is Jörðin 🌍
- it Terra 🌍
- iu ܕܢܘܗܐ
- jam Oert
- ja 地球 🌍
- jbo terdi
- jv Bumi
- kaa Jer
- kab Tagnit
- ka დედამიწა
- kg Ntoto
- kk Жер 🌍
- kl Nunarsuaq
- km ផែនដី
- kn ಭೂಮಿ
- koi Mywap
- ko 지구
- krc Джар
- ksh Ääd (Planeet)
- ku Erd

- Qualifiers
- Temporal data
- Data types
- Error ranges
- References

Data retrieval

- SPARQL
- Wikidata will give you all they *know*, but not more than that
- The more data there is, the more useful Wikidata is
- <https://query.wikidata.org>

Female mayors

```
9
10 ?city wdt:P31/wdt:P279* ?c . # find instances of subclasses of city
11 ?city p:P6 ?statement . # with a P6 (head of government) statement
12 ?statement ps:P6 ?mayor . # ... that has the value ?mayor
13 ?mayor wdt:P21 ?sex . # ... where the ?mayor has P21 (sex or gender) female
14 FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?statement pq:P582 ?x } # ... but the statement has no P582 (end date) qualifier
15
16 # Now select the population value of the ?city
17 # (wdt: properties use only statements of "preferred" rank if any, usually meaning "current population")
18 ?city wdt:P1082 ?population .
19 # Optionally, find English labels for city and mayor:
20 SERVICE wikibase:label {
21 bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "sr", "en" .
22 }
23 }
24 ORDER BY DESC(?population)
25 LIMIT 10
```

Press [CTRL-SPACE] to activate auto completion.

Data updated **a few seconds** ago

[Run](#) [Clear](#) 10 Results in 995 ms

[Display](#) [Download](#) [Link](#)

city	cityLabel	mayor	mayorLabel
Q1490	Токио	Q261703	Yuriko Koike
Q1156	Мумбај	Q18218029	Snehal Ambekar
Q38283	Јокохама	Q529363	Fumiko Hayashi
Q1533	Каракас	Q21573102	Helen Fernández
Q2807	Мадрид	Q19592761	Manuela Carmena
Q11462	Сурабаја	Q12522317	Tri Rismaharini
Q220	Рим	Q23766020	Вирџинија Рађи
Q90	Париз	Q2851133	Anne Hidalgo
Q16555	Хјустон	Q213847	Annise Parker
Q3915	Антананариво	Q14618311	Lalao Ravalomanana

Billionaires

item	itemLabel	billions
Q wd:Q5284	Бил Гејтс	77.7
Q wd:Q29279	Амансио Ортега	73.5
Q wd:Q47213	Ворен Бафет	60.8
Q wd:Q170419	Карлос Слим	49.9
Q wd:Q1066551	Charles G. Koch	42.9
Q wd:Q4934	Лари Пејџ	34.8
Q wd:Q92764	Сергеј Брин	34
Q wd:Q92764	Сергеј Брин	33.4
Q wd:Q92764	Сергеј Брин	32.6
Q wd:Q2105413	Wang Jianlin	28.7
Q wd:Q12908	Џорџ Сорос	24.9
Q wd:Q181162	Steve Ballmer	24.8
Q wd:Q557305	Phil Knight	23.4
Q wd:Q92764	Сергеј Брин	18.7
Q wd:Q293679	Al-Waleed bin Talal	18.3
Q wd:Q1394965	Aliko Dangote	18
Q wd:Q1225503	Dilip Shanghvi	17.5
Q wd:Q717038	Masayoshi Son	17
Q wd:Q92764	Сергеј Брин	16.6

Eponyms

eponym	eponymLabel	count	sample	sampleLabel
Q wd:Q41688	Хендрик Антон Лоренц	97	Q wd:Q172137	Лоренцова сила
Q wd:Q6722	Карл Фридрих Гаус	80	Q wd:Q2658	Gaussian elimination
Q wd:Q41585	Давид Хилберт	61	Q wd:Q190056	Хилбертов простор
Q wd:Q173746	Пал Ердеш	49	Q wd:Q243972	Ердешев број
Q wd:Q935	Исак Њутн	44	Q wd:Q12438	ЊУТН
Q wd:Q7604	Леонард Ојлер	43	Q wd:Q82435	е
Q wd:Q318362	Johan de Witt	42	Q wd:Q290492	HNLMS Johan de Witt
Q wd:Q42299	Bernhard Riman	36	Q wd:Q152860	4167 Riemann
Q wd:Q8814	Огистен Луј Коши	32	Q wd:Q45286	Cauchy–Binet formula
Q wd:Q9041	Џејмс Ват	29	Q wd:Q25236	ват
Q wd:Q23696	Simon Stevin	27	Q wd:Q1344596	Stevinus
Q wd:Q176659	Андреј Марков	25	Q wd:Q2733	Lempel–Ziv–Markov chain Algorithm
Q wd:Q80222	Жозеф Луј Лагранж	25	Q wd:Q190463	Лагранжова тачка
Q wd:Q153224	Андреј Колмогоров	24	Q wd:Q575766	Kolmogorov–Smirnov test
Q wd:Q77141	Александар Гротендик	24	Q wd:Q1062242	Grothendieck topology
Q wd:Q762	Леонардо да Винчи	23	Q wd:Q19101	Leonardo da Vinci–Fiumicino Airport
Q wd:Q17455	Џон фон Нојман	22	Q wd:Q77887	Von Neumann universe
Q wd:Q7251	Алан Тјуринг	21	Q wd:Q163310	Тјурингова машина
Q wd:Q44481	Пјер Симон Лаплас	20	Q wd:Q44666	Laplace's demon
Q wd:Q81082	Анри Поенкаре	19	Q wd:Q146944	2021 Поенкаре
Q wd:Q619	Никола Коперник	18	Q wd:Q1278	коперницијум

Cats

 commons:James bowen (author).jpeg
Bob
 wd:Q27744042

 commons:Ayasofya Gll cat.jpg
Gll
 wd:Q28792126

Mrs. Chippy
 commons:Mrschippy2.png
 wd:Q851190

Hodge
 commons:Hodgecat flickr.jpg
 wd:Q1622688

Scarlett
 commons:ScarlettTheCat.jpg
 wd:Q4421603

Mr. Nuts
 commons:Mr Nuts Executive Portrait.jpg
 wd:Q6928344

Tsim Tung Brother Cream
 commons:Brother cream in stall.jpg
 wd:Q10813994

Wars by country by year

Incidence of cancer by year

- | | | | | | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|-----------------------|----------------------|-------------------------|----------------------|-------------------------------|------------------------|------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Acute erythroid leukemia | Burkitt lymphoma | Ewing's sarcoma | Hodgkin's lymphoma | Merkel cell carcinoma | acute leukemia | acute lymphocytic leukemia | acute myeloid leukemia | adenocarcinoma of the lung | anus cancer |
| astrocytoma | bone cancer | brain cancer | breast cancer | cancer | carcinoma | cervical cancer | cholangiocarcinoma | chronic lymphocytic leukemia | chronic myeloid leukemia |
| colorectal cancer | duodenum cancer | esophageal cancer | gallbladder cancer | glioblastoma multiforme | head and neck cancer | hepatocellular carcinoma | intestinal cancer | kidney cancer | laryngeal cancer |
| leukemia | linitis plastica | liposarcoma | myelofibrosis | lung cancer | lymphoid leukemia | lymphoma | lymphoma | melanoma | mesothelioma |
| multiple myeloma | myelodysplastic syndrome | nasopharynx carcinoma | myeloid neoplasm | nasopharynx carcinoma | non-Hodgkin lymphoma | non-small-cell lung carcinoma | mantle cell lymphoma | oligodendroglioma | oral cavity cancer |
| osteosarcoma | ovarian cancer | pancreatic cancer | peritoneal carcinoma | prostate cancer | rectum cancer | renal cell carcinoma | ocular melanoma | rhabdomyosarcoma | skin cancer |
| small cell carcinoma | spinal cancer | stomach cancer | testicular cancer | throat cancer | thyroid cancer | renal pelvis carcinoma | urinary bladder cancer | uterine cancer | |

Airports of Belgium

Links

- <http://tools.wmflabs.org/wikidata-game/> - Gamification
- <http://tools.wmflabs.org/fist/wdfist/> - Image search
- <http://tools.wmflabs.org/mix-n-match/> - Linking to external databases
- <https://tools.wmflabs.org/scholia/> - Citations, papers, authors
- <https://tools.wmflabs.org/reasonator/> - Narrative view
- <http://tools.wmflabs.org/magnustools/#wikidata> - More...
- https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Tools/External_tools - Misc

Questions?

Thank you!

filip@vikimedija.org